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From Adaptive Co-management to Viable SSF Governance: Understanding resource management dynamics in the fishing communities of Tembak Bulusan and Morodemak, Demak region, Indonesia

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Table of Contents

1. Introduction.....	1
2. Methods	4
2.1 Sampling	4
2.2 Data Collection	4
3. Results.....	6
3.1 Tambak Bulusan, Demak, Indonesia	6
3.2. Purwoejo, Morodemak, Demak, Indonesia	9
3.3. Small-Scale Fisher Household Survey Comparison.....	14
3.4 Fishery and Institutional Leader Comparison of Adaptive Co-Management Rankings.....	15
4. Discussion.....	15
4.1 Presence of Adaptive Co-Management within Indonesian SSF.....	15
4.1.1 Presence of Adaptive Co-Management in Tambak Bulusan	15
4.1.2 Presence of Adaptive Co-Management in Purwoejo.....	18
4.2 Adaptive Co-Management Governance Transitions in SSF.....	20
4.2.1 Tambak Bulusan, Demak, Indonesia	20
4.2.2 Purwoejo, Morodemak, Demak, Indonesia	21
5. Conclusions.....	21
References.....	22

From Adaptive Co-management to Viable SSF Governance: Understanding resource management dynamics in the fishing communities of Tembak Bulusan and Morodemak, Demak region, Indonesia

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Abstract

Small-Scale Fisheries (SSF) governance has historically excluded small-scale fishers from participating in decision-making processes, negatively influencing millions of livelihoods. Governance of SSF is complex due to interactions between users and the environment, both with varying influence on the system. Indonesia is of particular importance for SSF governance due to its archipelagic structure, fishing culture and the direct link between economic viability and SSF. Indonesian SSF provide livelihood, nutrition, and food and economic security to millions of fishers. Indonesian SSF, however, face illegal and unreported fishing practices, fishing location disputes, pollution, poor living conditions, declining fish stocks, and extreme, volatile weather conditions. Effective governance strategies of SSF that are able to adapt to dynamic conditions within Indonesian SSF are critically needed. This research study aims to explore the strength of adaptive co-management indicators present within SSF in Indonesia, and how current management of SSF can be transitioned into adaptive co-management, aiding in the transition of SSF from vulnerability to viability. Adaptive co-management is a governance approach that combines co-management and adaptive management, while integrating the practices of learning-by-doing, social memory, and social networks into governance proceedings. Over 100 small-scale fishers completed household surveys, with more than ten semi-structured interviews being conducted with institutional, governmental, and fishery leaders to determine adaptive co-management indicators intersecting each SSF. Results indicate adaptive co-management is an effective governance approach for complex social-ecological systems such as SSF. Adaptive co-management additionally provides an avenue to facilitate vulnerable to viable SSF transitions. Long-term institutional support, effective capital building, and social capital were identified as the strongest indicators of adaptive co-management, marking these indicators as critical for future development in SSF.

Keywords Social-ecological system • governance • adaptive co-management • sustainability • small-scale fisheries

1. Introduction

Small-Scale Fisheries (SSF), as the name suggests, operate on a small-scale across the globe. Fishers within SSF use minimal technology, fish in local waters, sell fish locally or consume their catch, have boats less than 12 meters in length, and have a total boat weight of less than 5 GT (gigatons) (Bakiu et al., 2018; FAO, 2015; Mozumder et al., 2020). SSFs are additionally comprised of marginalized individuals, many of whom are women, citing the need for effective governance (Harper et al., 2020; Winter et al., 2023). Determining effective governance approaches that address the diverse socio-economic needs of small-scale fishers are critically needed.

Due to the complexity of SSF, they are further defined as social-ecological systems. A social-ecological system is a complex, self-organizing system that has social and ecological interactions intersecting it, with various users interacting and depending on the system (Bennett & Gosnell, 2015; Folke et al., 2002; McGinnis & Ostrom, 2014; Ostrom, 2009; Ostrom, 2007). Social and ecological interactions can create varying impacts on each other within the social-ecological system, calling for adaptive approaches that can characterize the complex linkages, feedback, and uncertainty within the system (Berkes & Nayak, 2018; Nayak, 2014; Nayak et al., 2016). Governance approaches that are able to adapt, change, and learn from dynamic conditions need to be explored for effective SSF governance.

Adaptive co-management is a governance approach that can be employed within SSF. Adaptive co-management is a governance approach implemented within social-ecological systems that relies on the ecological knowledge of local users, institutional linkages and connections, social capital, formal and informal networks, and learn-by-doing approaches, to refine and adapt to dynamic conditions occurring within social-ecological systems, building the systems adaptive capacity and resilience to uncertainty (Armitage, 2007; Armitage et al., 2009; Armitage et al., 2007; Berkes, 2007; Plummer et al., 2013; Folke et al., 2005). Adaptive co-management is a different form of governance than co-management or adaptive management as it requires, social capital, social networks at vertical and horizontal scales and learn-by-doing approaches (Armitage et al., 2009; Armitage, 2007; Folke et al., 2005; Plummer et al., 2013). Adaptive co-management applicability within fisheries needs to be explored further.

Adaptive co-management requires strong social capital. Social capital in adaptive co-management according to Armitage et al., (2009) and Folke et al., (2005) is the societal norms, exchanges, rules, networks between actors and institutions, and relationships of trust between stakeholders that enable actors of a social-ecological systems to work collaboratively and collectively. Within social capital trust is an essential requirement. Trust within adaptive co-management is critical, as when users of a common-pool resource trust the managers, a sense of community is established and the system's ability to work collaboratively is enhanced (Armitage et al., 2009; Folke et al., 2005). Without trust in an adaptive co-management users will not work collaboratively, causing conflicts to arise between individual users and managers (Folke et al., 2005). Having trustworthy managers in social-ecological systems, in local government, SSF management, and fish trading is vital for the successful governance of these systems. Leaders create partnerships among actors, mobilize and generate support and create linkages between actors inside and outside the system (Folke et al., 2005). To have successful adaptive co-management social capital must be present within the social-ecological system.

Along with social capital, social networks are an essential component of adaptive co-management governance in social-ecological systems. Social networks as described by Armitage et al., (2009), Berkes, (2007), and Folke et al., (2005), are the connections and linkages established between users of a social-ecological system and the institutions that encompass it. Social networks are complex within social-ecological systems due to the immense number of users that interact with them, creating vertical and horizontal linkages between people and organizations (Armitage et al., 2009; Berkes, 2007). Vertical linkages as described by Berkes, (2007), are the links between users and institutions at various geographical scales, linking users to institutions and users outside of the system. Horizontal linkages as described by Berkes, (2007), are the links between different levels of organization within the social-ecological system, such as links between various levels of government. Within adaptive co-management social networks at both vertical and horizontal scales are required for viability.

Lastly, an essential component of adaptive co-management is a learn-by-doing approach. A learn-by-doing approach is an approach to governance that utilizes users' social memory to adapt and manage change within social-ecological systems (Armitage et al., 2009; Armitage et al., 2007; Folke et al., 2005). Social memory as defined by Folke et al., (2005), and Armitage et al., (2009), is the past historical experiences of users who utilize and interact with the social-ecological system most frequently. Incorporating learning

within adaptive co-management increases the adaptive capacity and expertise that the social-ecological system has, increasing the system's ability of sense making in governance, allowing the system to respond to uncertainty (Armitage et al., 2007; Folke et al., 2005; Plummer et al., 2013). Incorporating learning within adaptive co-management additionally, allows for flexible and continuous feedback from users of the social-ecological system, increasing the expertise for governance (Berkes, 2007). To have successful governance in social-ecological systems, learn-by-doing approaches are vital.

The current governance of SSF, however, has not successfully addressed vulnerabilities faced by small-scale fishers. SSF continue to be excluded from governance processes within the fisheries sector, increasing vulnerabilities including competition, fish stock decline, and exploitation of fishery resources (Issacs, 2013; FAO, 2015; Sowman et al., 2014; Mozumder et al., 2020; Winter et al., 2023). Top-down, command-and-control powered governance of SSF is continuing to strengthen vulnerabilities faced by small-scale fishers, as governance approaches do not address the socio-economic characteristics of small-scale fishers (Mozumder et al., 2020). Effective governance strategies for SSF must be able to adapt to dynamic conditions and address diverse economic, social and environmental characteristics of fishers and the fishery. This paper will investigate SSF governance in Indonesia. Indonesia is an important study site for research in SSF governance because they are the largest archipelagic country in the world, with 54% of animal consumption coming from fish (Warren & Steenbergen, 2021). In 2015 there were approximately six million fishers in Indonesia that were directly reliant on the production of SSF, with over 90% of fisheries production coming from SSF, marking Indonesia as the second largest marine capture fisheries producer in the world (Warren & Steenbergen, 2021; FAO, 2024). However, small-scale fishers in Indonesia have received little attention, even though their livelihoods are under immediate pressure from fisheries collapse (Warren & Steenbergen, 2021; FAO, 2024). Halima et al., (2019) states that Indonesia SSF require increased governance attention because these fisheries are not regulated and have their own set of rules and norms. Additionally, Warren & Steenbergen, (2021), state that more attention is required in the small-scale fishing sector in Indonesia. Effective governance strategies for SSF within Indonesia are imperative for the sustained livelihoods of Indonesian small-scale fishers.

The study sites of SSF within Indonesia for this paper require investigation into the governance processes and the relationships these processes have on fisher livelihoods. Within the two study sites for this thesis fishers do not have great relationships and connections to officials who partake in governance processes. Governance within the two Indonesian study sites for this thesis is complex, as there are a variety of actors, federal, provincial (state) and local governments who monitor and enforce varies rules and regulations. These regulations combat those rules, norms and traditions of fishers within these communities impacting the livelihoods of fishers. Understanding and strengthening the governance processes that intersect SSF are vital for these Indonesian communities. Effective governance strategies for SSF within Indonesia are imperative for the sustained livelihoods of Indonesian small-scale fishers.

This chapter seeks to fill the following gaps in Indonesian SSF literature on adaptive co-management and, while also generating knowledge on effective governance for SSF.

- 1) Armitage, (2007), states that there have been difficulties increasing the adaptation of social-ecological systems in common-pool resources where livelihoods are closely connected to the outcomes of the system.
- 2) Berkes, (2011) notes that more attention is needed in SSF governance in social-ecological systems to understand the dynamic change and management needs of the system.
- 3) Warren & Steenbergen, (2021), state that more attention is needed in the relationships and governance of SSF in Indonesia.
- 4) Halima et al., (2019) state that Indonesia SSF require increased governance attention because fisheries are not regulated and have their own rules and norms.

The objective of this chapter is to determine the adaptive co-management indicators present within two SSF in Indonesia to determine how adaptive co-management can be transitioned to as a form of SSF governance.

2. Methods

2.1 Sampling

To identify the specific communities of study for this chapter, purposeful sampling was conducted. The sampling criteria when purposefully selecting the SSF of Tambak Bulusan and Purwoejo were:

- (1) Must be a community with at least 50% of its members being small-scale fishers.
- (2) The community must be relatively close to Semarang, Indonesia.
- (3) There must be co-management or collaborative management practices already established in the communities.
- (4) The communities must have connections to the Universitas of Diponegoro, Indonesia.

Based on this criteria the SSF of Tambak Bulusan, Demak, Indonesia, and Purwoejo, Morodemak, Demak, Indonesia were selected.

Once the two SSF were selected small-scale fishers from each respective SSF were purposefully selected. The purposeful selection criteria for small-scale fishers in Tambak Bulusan and Purwoejo were as follows:

- 1) The small-scale fisher must have a fishing vessel with a total weight of 5 GT (gigatons) or less.
- 2) The small-scale fisher must be from either Tambak Bulusan or Purwoejo.
- 3) The small-scale fisher must have been participating in the SSF sector for at least five years.
- 4) The majority of the income for the small-scale fisher must come from small-scale fishing activities.

After this round of purposeful sampling a total of 119 small-scale fishers were sampled to complete household surveys across the two SSF, Tambak Bulusan (40) and Purwoejo (79).

After household surveys were completed with small-scale fishers, fishery and institutional leaders were purposefully sampled for semi-structured interviews in the fishing communities of Tambak Bulusan and Purwoejo. Leaders for the semi-structured interviews were purposefully selected within each SSF by meeting the following criteria:

- 1) Must be a leader (fishery, government, or academic) in the community.
- 2) Must be partnered with Tambak Bulusan or Purwoejo, Morodemak.
- 3) Must work with small-scale fishers in the community.
- 4) Must be in a current position of leadership for at least three years in their respective community.

After purposeful sampling 12 fishery and institutional leaders were interviewed across the two SSF, 6 from Tambak Bulusan and 6 from Purwoejo, Morodemak.

Therefore, after purposeful sampling was completed the total number of respondents for this chapter were 119 small-scale fishers and 12 fishery and institutional leaders across two SSF in Indonesia.

2.2 Data Collection

To collect data on the adaptive co-management indicators intersecting two SSF in Indonesia various forms of data collection methods were employed. These included qualitative observations, household surveys and semi-structured interviews. Multiple forms of data were gathered to support the central phenomenon and

ensure validation of the research results (Creswell & Creswell, 2023). First, qualitative observations were conducted regarding the adaptive co-management indicators observed in the communities when in public settings and around the SSF. Qualitative observations as defined by Creswell & Creswell, (2023) are the observations of researchers in the field that are written in unstructured and open formats within a researcher's journal. Observational notes were written down in a researcher's journal as they occurred and at the end of every day.

Indicator	Works Evolved From
Well-Defined Resource System	Armitage et al., 2007; Armitage et al., 2009; Pomeroy and Williams, 1994; Susilowati and Budiati, 2003; Ostrom, 1990; Ostrom, 1994.
Community Collectivity	Pomeroy and Williams, 1994; Susilowati and Budiati, 2003; Pomeroy et al., 2001; Ostrom, 1990; Ostrom, 2007.
Clear Property Rights	Armitage et al., 2007; Armitage et al., 2009; Ostrom 1990; Pomeroy and Williams, 1994; Susilowati and Budiati, 2003; Pomeroy et al., 2001; Ostrom, 2007.
Access to Adaptable Management Portfolio	Armitage et al., 2007; Armitage et al., 2009; Berkes, 2007; Berkes, 2009; Folke et al., 2005.
Institutional Support	Armitage et al., 2007; Armitage et al., 2009; Berkes, 2007; Berkes, 2009; Pomeroy, 1993.
Capital Building	Armitage et al., 2007; Armitage et al., 2009; Berkes, 2009; Berkes, 2007; Pomeroy et al., 2001; Islam et al, 2023; Ostrom, 2007; Carlson and Berkes, 2005; Folke et al., 2005.
Leadership	Armitage et al., 2007; Armitage et al., 2009; Pomeroy and Williams, 1994; Susilowati and Budiati, 2003; Pomeroy et al., 2001; Berkes, 2007.
Community Participation	Pomeroy and Williams, 1994; Susilowati and Budiati, 2003; Ostrom, 1990; Pomeroy et al., 2001.
Delegation of Authority	Pomeroy, 1993; Susilowati and Budiati, 2003; Pomeroy and Williams, 1994; Pomeroy et al., 2001; Berkes, 2007; Armitage et al., 2009.
Community Empowerment	Pomeroy et al., 2001; Pomeroy and Williams, 1994; Susilowati and Budiati, 2003.

(Adapted from: Armitage et al., 2007; Armitage et al., 2009; Berkes, 2009; Berkes, 2007; Carlson and Berkes, 2005; Folke et al., 2005; Islam et al, 2023; Ostrom, 1990; Ostrom, 1994; Ostrom, 2007; Pomeroy et al., 2001; Pomeroy and Williams, 1994; Pomeroy, 1993; Susilowati and Budiati, 2003)

After qualitative observations were completed, household surveys were conducted with small-scale fishers within each SSF. Household surveys for small-scale fishers were designed to examine the adaptive co-management indicators intersecting the SSF. The household surveys employed with small-scale fishers included 10 adaptive co-management indicators to be tested (Table 1). These adaptive co-management

indicators were developed through extensive review of current adaptive co-management and co-management indicators for successful implementation in coastal communities, combining the works of various scholars.

After small-scale fishers completed household surveys, these household surveys were analyzed to create interview questions for fishery and institutional leaders with each SSF. Questions to fishery and institutional leaders focused on areas that were essential to adaptive co-management identified through literature review and the indicators from small-scale fisher household surveys that needed further expansion. Questions to the academic partners both SSF were different from those asked to fishery and institutional leaders. These questions centered around institutional support, capital building, adaptable management and social networks. The interviews conducted with fishery and institutional leaders were semi-structured, which allowed the researchers to interchange the questions as per the responses of the interviewee and add additional questions to the interview based on the responses provided (Knott et al., 2022). This allowed the most amount of information to be obtained from interview participants.

3. Results

3.1 Tambak Bulusan, Demak, Indonesia

40 small-scale fishers completed household surveys to understand the adaptive co-management dynamics intersecting the SSF of Tambak Bulusan. Table 2 identifies a summary of the collective responses of all 40 small-scale fishers who completed household surveys in Tambak Bulusan. Table 2 indicates the adaptive co-management indicator, and the total agree, disagree, and uncertain responses from 40 small-scale fishers in Tambak Bulusan. Some indicators in Table 2 have more total responses than other indicators. This is because Table 2 summarizes the total amount of responses from all small-scale fishers' household surveys in Tambak Bulusan.

ACM Indicator	Small-Scale Fisher Response		
	Agree	Disagree	Uncertain
Well Defined Resource System	121	21	18
Community Collectivity	141	19	0
Clear Property Rights	94	24	2
Accessible Adaptable Management Portfolio	141	16	3
Institutional Support	145	48	7
Capital Building	81	35	4
Leadership	176	21	3
Participation	65	53	4
Delegation of Authority	122	16	22
Community Empowerment	63	14	3

(Source: Primary Household Survey Data, 2024)

After household surveys were completed with small-scale fishers in Tambak Bulusan, 6 Semi-structured interviews with fishery and institutional leaders were conducted. These interviews expanded on the results

found in household surveys, with small-scale fishers, while also determining what adaptive co-management indicators leaders and institutional partners believed were the most imperative for their communities.

Table 3 below provides an overview of a ranking of the 10 adaptive co-management indicators tested in Tambak Bulusan from fishery and institutional leaders. Table 3 indicates the rank of the adaptive co-management indicator, what the adaptive co-management indicator was, the number of fishery and institutional leaders that noted the indicator's importance, followed by the total percentage of fishery and institutional leaders that noted the adaptive co-management indicator.

Rank	Adaptive Co-Management Indicator	Number of Respondents	Percentage of Total Interview Respondents
1	Institutional Support	6	100%
1	Capital Building	6	100%
2	Adaptive Management Portfolio	5	83.33%
3	Leadership	4	66.67%
4	Participation	3	50%
4	Delegation of Authority	3	50%
5	Clear Property Rights	2	33.33%
6	Community Empowerment	1	16.67%
7	Community Collectivity	0	0%
7	Well-Defined Resource System	0	0%

(Source: Primary Semi-Structured Interview Data, 2024)

Table 4 indicates the fishery and institutional leader responses from Tambak Bulusan, and what each leader had to say about specific adaptive co-management indicators. Table 4 identifies the adaptive co-management indicator, the leader or institutional partner that mentioned it and a quote of what the leader or institutional partner stated.

ACM Indicator	Leader Title in Community	Quote
Clear Property Rights	Community Tourism Leader	"This means that all efforts made by Bumdes must be managed together with the residents of Tambakbulusan village."
Adaptable Management Portfolio	Local Village Governmental Leader	"Previous experience gives us a better understanding of what we need to do now. The most common form of development is the use of newer fishing gear, considering the effectiveness of the catch."
	Academic Institution	"The community there faces problems in managing fisheries productivity, but there is still ecotourism to help alleviate the problem during the low season."

Institutional Support	Community Tourism Leader	"Many UNDIP academics help here: tourism infrastructure development, mangrove planting, business management education, and tourism area management. Many collaborations have been carried out with UNDIP as a partner to encourage the development of this tourism."
	Academic Institution	"Currently, we also have fostered MSMEs in Bulusan ponds, where they work selling processed fishery products from their community, and various financial management training and education in their management, so that they can provide added value to fishery products."
	SSF Leader	"At least, here every 3 months there will definitely be counseling and training held by the local government, so that it can help provide knowledge to fishermen about how to manage the fishery products."
Capital Building	SSF Leader	"The assistance from the university for tourism development itself I admit is very much, UNDIP in tourism development assistance here alone can reach hundreds of millions of rupiah. But not directly to fishermen because there are several other types of groups there, starting from mangroves, micro businesses/traders, and fisheries cultivation."
		"The perception of fishermen in the past was that when they got it, they sold it directly, but because they have received training, now some are stored for food stock when the lean season occurs. Education and training can also drive social progress in the community here."
	Manager of Fish Processing and Trading	"Forms of incentives such as training and coaching are often carried out by the government and academics given to the community".
	Local Village Governmental Leader	"Currently we are providing training and counseling and coordinating with related agencies in providing guidance to the community's livelihoods."
	SSF Leader	"What we need now is a lot of training and coaching, especially in managing fish catches."
Leadership	SSF Leader	"We went through a group deliberation meeting. But until today no one wants to replace me in managing this fishermen's group. Because my social network is large, starting from the village, local government, and fisheries managers."

	Local Village Governmental Leader	"For the fishermen group, it is selected through a member meeting, then ask for a letter of recommendation from the village head to make a letter to the district government. While the village head is selected through a general election."
	SSF Leader	"It comes from a discussion of the members of the fishermen's group, [...] At least every 2 months we have regular meetings to discuss existing fishermen's problems."
Participation	Local Village Governmental Leader	"(Greater incentives) are very necessary. Especially now there are many complaints and problems that occur in the fisheries sector, not only in the form of assistance with tools and materials, but also other support from coaching and direction carried out in the livelihoods of these fishermen."
	SSF Leader	"Evidence 10 years ago before the massive destructive fishing gear, the community here could harvest fish with nets alone, reaching 100-150 kg in one trip to sea."
Delegation of Authority	SSF Leader	"I think it's fair now. If you look at the profit and loss, the government never expects profit. Because they share knowledge and technology with us."
Community Empowerment	Academic Institution	"Connectivity provides great benefits for the local communities of [...] Tambak Bulusan. UNDIP provides large funding to be developed through research and educational transfer (as I did), so this is very helpful in developing the local community there."

(Source: Primary Semi-Structured Interview Data, 2024)

Table 4 above does not have any mention of two of the ten adaptive co-management indicators, a well-defined resource system and community collectivity. This is due to fishery leaders and institutional partners in Tambak Bulusan not mentioned heavy importance on these adaptive co-management indicators.

3.2. Purwoejo, Morodemak, Demak, Indonesia

79 small-scale fishers participated in household surveys aimed to understand the adaptive co-management dynamics intersecting the SSF of Purwoejo. Table 5 identifies a collective summary of the responses from all 79 small-scale fishers in Purwoejo who completed household surveys on adaptive co-management indicators intersecting their community. Table 5 indicates the adaptive co-management indicator, and the total agree, disagree, and uncertain responses from 79 small-scale fishers surveyed in Purwoejo. Some indicators in Table 5 have more total responses than others. This is due to the total number of questions used to examine each adaptive co-management indicator.

Table 5
Summary of the Small-Scale Fisher Responses Within Purwoejo on Adaptive Co-Management Indicators Intersecting Their Community

ACM Indicator	Small-Scale Fisher Response		
	Agree	Disagree	Uncertain
Well Defined Resource System	212	98	6
Community Collectivity	226	78	12
Clear Property Rights	141	55	41
Accessible Adaptable Management Portfolio	238	73	5
Institutional Support	155	197	43
Capital Building	140	90	7
Leadership	208	138	49
Participation	142	76	19
Delegation of Authority	216	27	73
Community Empowerment	107	48	3

(Source: Primary Household Survey Data, 2024)

After household surveys were completed with small-scale fishers in Purwoejo, 6 Semi-structured interviews with fishery and institutional leaders were conducted. These interviews expanded results found in household surveys, while also determining what adaptive co-management indicators leaders and institutional partners believed to be the most influential.

Table 6 below provides a ranking overview of the 10 adaptive co-management indicators tested in Purwoejo from fishery and institutional leaders. Table 6 indicates the rank of the adaptive co-management indicator, what the adaptive co-management indicator was, the number of fishery and institutional leaders that noted the indicator's importance, followed by the total percentage of fishery and institutional leaders that noted the adaptive co-management indicator.

Table 6
Ranking the Adaptive Co-Management Indicators Based on Importance as Discovered in Semi-Structured Interviews with Fishery and Institutional Leaders in Purwoejo

Rank	Adaptive Co-Management Indicator	Number of Interviews Respondents	Percentage of Total Interview Respondents
1	Institutional Support	6	100%
1	Capital Building	6	100%
2	Leadership	5	83.33%
3	Accessible Adaptive Management Portfolio	4	66.67%
3	Community Collectivity	4	66.67%
4	Delegation of Authority	3	50%
4	Participation	3	50%

4	Clear Property Rights	3	50%
5	Well-Defined Resource System	1	16.67%
5	Community Empowerment	1	16.67%

(Source: Primary Semi-Structured Interview Data, 2024)

Table 7 indicates the fishery and institutional leader responses from Purwoejo, and what each leader had to say about specific adaptive co-management indicators. Table 7 identifies the adaptive co-management indicator, the leader or institutional partner that mentioned it and a quote of what the leader or institutional partner stated.

Table 7		
<i>Semi-Structured Interview Responses from Fishery and Institutional Leaders in Tabak Bulusan regarding adaptive co-management indicators</i>		
ACM Indicator	Leader Title in Community	Quote
Well-Defined Resource System	Head of Purwoejo Fishing Port	"The provincial government has the authority to regulate and manage marine resources from a distance of 0-12 miles, then the national authority is above 12 miles-200 miles (EEZ). While for land management (TPI and fishermen) is the task of the district government."
Community Collectivity	Head of Purwoejo Fishing Port	"If we follow the fisheries law, then the number of fishermen here is around 300 people."
	Head of Purwoejo Fishing Port	"Many fishing gears do not comply with the limits that have been given. For example, there are several destructive fishing gears: "arad" (mini trawl), "sodo" (kuznet). This has a damaging effect on the ecosystem and marine resources."
	SSF Leader	"If the rainy season, this "butterfly" fishing gear can be more than 100 people, because in that season the type of anchovy is abundant."
Community Collectivity	Academic Institution	"(Purwoejo) has a bigger problem, because the fishing community is very large in the Morodemak area."
Clear Property Rights	Head of Purwoejo Fishing Port	"In terms of supervision, there is good cooperation from the fisheries and maritime services, the Directorate of Water and Air Police, and also from the Indonesian Navy. So, we share the risk of supervision with these government institutions, to ensure that fishermen catch fish in accordance with the permits that have been given."

	Head of Woman Fishers and Processors	There are various agencies that usually help in fisheries management, starting from the marine and fisheries service (province - district), the Marine and Air Police Corps, the environmental service, the local government (district). They have various tasks and authorities here in regulating the management of fish here."
Accessible Adaptive Management Portfolio	Head of Purwoejo Fishing Port	"We currently base management on the problems that occur."
	SSF Leader	"There are many previous experiences, starting from the stories of our predecessors that have become knowledge for many fishermen here."
	SSF Aquaculture Leader	"We also often get help from academics (usually from UNDIP) to carry out better pond cultivation management."
	Head of Purwoejo Fishing Port	"From the Central Java provincial government. Several programs that are currently being run, one of which is increasing fishermen's income. The program is also one way to secure marine resources and ecosystems. There is a fish apartment program that is useful for restoring coral reef and fish ecosystems, so that it can create fishing grounds that are closer to the coast and can also reduce their production costs."
		"We together with the government and local communities are looking for solutions to provide decent and legal housing, so that coastal area management can be achieved."
	Academic Institution	"Datares, Wetlands and JICA. These NGOs handle coastal area conservation and coastal community management, so they are very helpful to us and also the Morodemak [...] communities in transferring knowledge and technology. Currently we also have a connectivity program between local communities and the local government of Demak Regency, the Central Java government, and the central government (national). We have a strong relationship with the Ministry of Marine Affairs and Fisheries, where they have a funding program for the rehabilitation of the Morodemak coastal area."
		"Usually in the form of training and counseling. For example, just yesterday there was a ship engine repair training, where they also received assistance in the form of 1 set of ship engine repair tools."

	SSF Leader	"Fishermen here are still demanding easy access to resources and assistance that can be provided by the government."
Capital Building	Head of Woman Fishers and Processors	"The form of assistance here is usually not in the form of cash (money capital). But in the form of fishing gear, boat engines, administrative assistance, fishermen's insurance, and forms of training conducted to encourage increased fishermen's capacity."
	SSF Leader	"Here at the moment we only get fuel subsidy assistance, each member gets a fuel subsidy of 2 liters/per day."
	Academic Institution	"Undip provides large funding to be developed through research and educational transfer (as I did), so this is very helpful in developing the local community there."
		"Conducting a master plan to increase knowledge about the threat to the local community. What we do is coastal public space area management, rehabilitation, and increasing economic capacity."
Leadership	SSF Aquaculture Leader	"Voting and deliberation were carried out to determine the group leader."
	Head of Women Fishers and Processors	"Through deliberation, where the formation of the fishermen group is at least 15 members. Deliberation to determine the chairman, secretary, and treasurer."
Participation		"As long as you have a group, you will often be included in activities carried out together with government agencies."
	SSF Leader	"Currently, fuel subsidies must receive recommendations from fishermen groups, so to get a share of fuel subsidies, they must join a group. Because, the government cannot help individuals, the requirement to receive assistance from the government at this time is to have a joint business group (KUB)."
	SSF Leader	"Competition between fishermen, related to the differences in fishing gear used. Currently we are competing with environmentally unfriendly tools."

Delegation of Authority	Head of Purwoejo Fishing Port	"Collaboration is carried out from the national level to the village level, from the national government side, contributing from the budget to solve these problems (starting from cleaning sedimentation, rehabilitation, mangroves, and coastal embankments)."
	SSF Leader	"There is legitimacy, usually there is an introduction from the sub-district, notary, and later it will be submitted to the Maritime Affairs and Fisheries Service."

(Source: Primary Semi-Structured Interview Data, 2024)

3.3. Small-Scale Fisher Household Survey Comparison

Table 8 indicates a comparison between the two SSF of Tambak Bulusan and Purwoejo, Morodemak, Demak, Indonesia. Table 8 indicates the responses from small-scale fisher household surveys in each SSF and their responses of agree, disagree, and uncertain to adaptive co-management indicators intersecting their respective communities.

Tambak Bulusan, Demak, Indonesia			Purwoejo, Morodemak, Demak, Indonesia		
Rank	Adaptive Co-Management Indicator	Number of Fishers Agreeing with Indicator	Rank	Adaptive Co-Management Indicator	Number of Fishers Agreeing with Indicator
1	Leadership	176	1	Accessible Adaptable Management Portfolio	238
2	Institutional Support	145	2	Community Collectivity	226
3	Community Collectivity	141	3	Delegation of Authority	216
3	Accessible Adaptive Management Portfolio	141	4	A Well-Defined Resource System	212
4	Delegation of Authority	122	5	Leadership	208
5	A Well-Defined Resource System	121	6	Institutional Support	155
6	Clear Property Rights	94	7	Participation	142
7	Capital Building	81	8	Clear Property Rights	141
8	Participation	65	9	Capital Building	140
9	Community Empowerment	63	10	Community Empowerment	107

(Source: Primary Household Survey Data, 2024)

3.4 Fishery and Institutional Leader Comparison of Adaptive Co-Management Rankings

Table 9 indicates the fishery and institutional leader rankings of adaptive co-management indicators across both Tambak Bulusan and Purwoejo. Table 9 for each SSF indicates the rank of the adaptive co-management indicator, what the indicator is, the number of fishery and institutional leaders that noted its importance and the total percentage of fishery and institutional leaders that mentioned the indicator's importance.

Tambak Bulusan, Demak, Indonesia				Purwoejo, Morodemak, Demak, Indonesia			
Rank	Adaptive Co-Management Indicator	Number of Respondents	Percentage of Total Interview Respondents	Rank	Adaptive Co-Management Indicator	Number of Interviews Respondents	Percentage of Total Interview Respondents
1	Institutional Support	6	1	1	Institutional Support	6	1
1	Capital Building	6	1	1	Capital Building	6	1
2	Adaptive Management Portfolio	5	0.8333	2	Leadership	5	0.8333
3	Leadership	4	0.6667	3	Accessible Adaptive Management Portfolio	4	0.6667
4	Participation	3	0.5	3	Community Collectivity	4	0.6667
4	Delegation of Authority	3	0.5	4	Delegation of Authority	3	0.5
5	Clear Property Rights	2	0.3333	4	Participation	3	0.5
6	Community Empowerment	1	0.1667	4	Clear Property Rights	3	0.5
7	Community Collectivity	0	0	5	Well-Defined Resource System	1	0.1667
7	Well-Defined Resource System	0	0	5	Community Empowerment	1	0.1667

(Source: Primary Semi-Structured Interview Data, 2024)

4. Discussion

4.1 Presence of Adaptive Co-Management within Indonesian SSF

4.1.1 Presence of Adaptive Co-Management in Tambak Bulusan

In the SSF of Tambak Bulusan, Demak, Indonesia adaptive co-management indicators are perceived and felt differently between small-scale fishers and fishery and institutional leaders. Table 10 indicates a comparison of the adaptive co-management indicators noted by small-scale fishers and fishery and institutional leaders in Tambak Bulusan. Table 10 small-scale fisher results (Green) were adopted and

ranked from Table 2 which summarized the results from household surveys. Fishery and institutional leader results in Table 10 (Blue) were adopted from Table 3 and indicate the respective ranking of adaptive co-management indicators based on semi-structured interviews.

Tambak Bulusan Small-Scale Fisher Adaptive Co-Management Rankings from Household Surveys			Tambak Bulusan Fishery and Institutional Leaders Ranking of Adaptive Co-Management Importance from Interviews			
Rank	Adaptive Co-Management Indicator	Number of Fishers Agreeing with Indicator	Rank	Adaptive Co-Management Indicator	Number of Respondents	Percentage of Total Interview Respondents
1	Leadership	176	1	Institutional Support	6	1
2	Institutional Support	145	1	Capital Building	6	1
3	Community Collectivity	141	2	Adaptive Management Portfolio	5	0.8333
3	Accessible Adaptive Management Portfolio	141	3	Leadership	4	0.6667
4	Delegation of Authority	122	4	Participation	3	0.5
5	A Well-Defined Resource System	121	4	Delegation of Authority	3	0.5
6	Clear Property Rights	94	5	Clear Property Rights	2	0.3333
7	Capital Building	81	6	Community Empowerment	1	0.1667
8	Participation	65	7	Community Collectivity	0	0
9	Community Empowerment	63	7	Well-Defined Resource System	0	0

(Source: Primary Household Survey & Semi-Structured Interview Data, 2024)

Results from Table 10 exemplify different results between small-scale fishers and fishery and institutional leaders regarding the ranking of adaptive co-management indicators. Table 10 indicates that small-scale fishers identified; leadership, institutional support and community collectivity as the top three adaptive co-management indicators within their community. While fishery and institutional leaders in Table 10 noted the top three adaptive co-management indicators of institutional support, capital building and an adaptable management portfolio. This highlights the need to include all users of SSF into governance decision-making processes as what are priorities for fishery and institutional leaders are not the same for the small-scale fishers.

Small-scale fishers noted in Table 10 that the number 1 most influential and present adaptive co-management indicator within the community is leadership. This is different from the results obtained from fishery and institutional leader within Tambak Bulusan. Fishery and institutional leaders noted leadership as the third most influential adaptive co-management indicator in Tambak Bulusan. Institutional support dynamics were of similar importance to small-scale fishers and fishery and institutional leaders in Tambak

Bulusan. Small-scale fishers noted institutional support as second, while fishery and institutional leaders noted institutional support as the most influential and present dynamic of adaptive co-management. Lastly, small-scale fishers note community collectivity as the third most influential and present adaptive co-management indicator intersecting the fishery. While fishery and institutional leaders noted community collectivity as one of the least important adaptive co-management indicators (see Table 10).

Fishery and institutional leaders in Tambak Bulusan noted in Table 10 that the along with institutional support, the most present and influential adaptive co-management indicator was capital building. This is different from the results obtained from small-scale fishers in Tambak Bulusan as fishers ranked capital building, seventh in terms of adaptive co-management importance. In second, fishery and institutional leaders indicated access to an adaptable management portfolio as essential for adaptive co-management. This was similar to the results obtained from small-scale fishers in Tambak Bulusan, as fishers noted access to an adaptable management portfolio was at the same influential and importance level as community collectivity.

These differences in importance of adaptive co-management indicators identified by small-scale fishers and fishery and institutional leaders within Tambak Bulusan, highlight the importance of continued research in SSF. This has also been noted from other scholars such as Warren & Steenbergen, (2021), who state increased research is needed in SSF within Indonesia. Also, Berkes, (2011), notes that more attention is needed to SSF governance. This is due to the fact that the needs of small-scale fishers are different from those leading and partnering within the community, as can be observed from Table 10.

There are also differences between the adaptive co-management indicators discovered and ranked in Table 9 compared to the adaptive co-management indicators noted as essential in the literature. Current literature within adaptive co-management, however, has noted essential characteristics for adaptive co-management as social capital (trust and leaderships) (Armitage et al., 2009; Folke et al., 2005), social networks and linkages (institutional support) (Armitage et al., 2009; Berkes, 2007; Folke et al., 2005), and a learn-by-doing approach (adaptive management portfolio) (Armitage et al., 2009; Armitage et al., 2007; Folke et al., 2005; Plummer et al., 2013). Small-scale fishers noted leadership (social capital) and institutional support (social networks) as two key dynamics for adaptive co-management just as the literature does. However, small-scale fishers in Tambak Bulusan also noted how community collectivity as an essential dynamic for governance to be successful within SSF.

Fishery and institutional leaders also indicated institutional support (social networks) and an adaptive management portfolio (learn-by-doing approach) as two essential dynamics influencing adaptive co-management within their SSF. However, Table 10 indicates that fishery and institutional leaders noted capital building as an essential adaptive co-management indicator. Capital building is similar to institutional support, however fishery and institutional leaders noted in Table 4 that there is a need for increased capital building within the community because it has the power to increase small-scale fisher capacity, income and knowledge. Additionally, in Table 4 fishery and institutional leaders noted there are a variety of social programs being conducted supporting fisher livelihoods, but very few monetary programs within the community.

Therefore, Table 10 indicates the ranking of adaptive co-management indicator importance within Tambak Bulusan based on small-scale fisher household surveys and fishery and institutional leader interviews. Table 10 exemplified similar results to the essential adaptive co-management indicators needed for successful adaptive co-management implementation as stated in the literature. However, disparities between the literature and the community were found. Additionally, disparities between fishery and institutional leader and small-scale fishers themselves were found within Tambak Bulusan.

4.1.2 Presence of Adaptive Co-Management in Purwoejo

In the SSF of Purwoejo, Morodemak, Demak, Indonesia adaptive co-management indicators are perceived and felt differently between small-scale fishers and fishery and institutional leaders within the community. Table 11 indicates a comparison of the adaptive co-management indicators noted by small-scale fishers and fishery and institutional leaders in Purwoejo. The small-scale fisher results (Green) were adopted and ranked from Table 5 that summarized the results from household surveys with small-scale fishers. The fishery and institutional leader rankings of adaptive co-management indicators (Blue) for Table 11 were adopted from Table 6.

Table 11						
<i>Comparison of Adaptive Co-Management Indicator Rankings for Small-Scale Fishers and Fishery and Institutional Leaders in Purwoejo</i>						
Purwoejo Small-Scale Fisher Adaptive Co-Management Rankings from Household Surveys			Purwoejo Fishery and Institutional Leaders Ranking of Adaptive Co-Management Importance from Interviews			
Rank	Adaptive Co-Management Indicator	Number of Fishers Agreeing with Indicator	Rank	Adaptive Co-Management Indicator	Number of Interviews Respondents	Percentage of Total Interview Respondents
1	Accessible Adaptable Management Portfolio	238	1	Institutional Support	6	1
2	Community Collectivity	226	1	Capital Building	6	1
3	Delegation of Authority	216	2	Leadership	5	0.8333
4	A Well-Defined Resource System	212	3	Accessible Adaptive Management Portfolio	4	0.6667
5	Leadership	208	3	Community Collectivity	4	0.6667
6	Institutional Support	155	4	Delegation of Authority	3	0.5
7	Participation	142	4	Participation	3	0.5
8	Clear Property Rights	141	4	Clear Property Rights	3	0.5
9	Capital Building	140	5	Well-Defined Resource System	1	0.1667
10	Community Empowerment	107	5	Community Empowerment	1	0.1667

(Source: Primary Household Survey & Semi-Structured Interview Data, 2024)

Results from Table 11 exemplify adaptive co-management indicators noted as important by small-scale fishers and those for fishery and institutional leaders in Purwoejo. Table 11 indicates that small-scale fishers in Purwoejo noted, accessible adaptive management portfolio, community collectivity and delegation of authority as the important adaptive co-management indicators intersecting the community. While Table 11 indicated that fishery and institutional leaders in Purwoejo noted, institutional support, capital building and leadership as the top adaptive co-management indicators intersecting the community. These results between small-scale fishers and fishery and institutional leaders in Purwoejo highlight the importance of continued research in the governance of SSF, as fishers and leaders have varying needs.

Small-scale fishers in Purwoejo noted that having access to an adaptive management portfolio is the most important adaptive co-management indicator (see Table 11). While fishery and institutional leaders ranked access to an adaptive management portfolio third. For the second most influential and prominent adaptive co-management indicator present within Purwoejo, small-scale fishers noted community collectivity. While fishery and institutional leaders noted community collectivity as tied for third with accessible adaptable management portfolio (see Table 11). Lastly, small-scale fishers noted delegation of authority as the third most influential adaptive co-management dynamic in Purwoejo, in Table 11. While fishery and institutional leaders noted delegation of authority as the fourth most important and influential adaptive co-management dynamic.

Fishery and institutional leaders noted institutional support as the most influential and important adaptive co-management indicator intersecting Purwoejo. While small-scale fishers in Purwoejo had ranked institutional support as the sixth most important adaptive co-management dynamic intersecting the community (see Table 11). Next, fishery and institutional leaders noted capital building as equally important to institutional support within Purwoejo. While small-scale fishers noted capital building as the ninth most influential adaptive co-management indicator intersecting Purwoejo (see Table 11). Lastly, fishery and institutional leaders noted leadership as the second most influential adaptive co-management indicator in Purwoejo. While small-scale fishers in Purwoejo note leadership as the fifth most important adaptive co-management indicator intersecting Purwoejo.

Along with differences between small-scale fishers and fishery and institutional leaders within Purwoejo, adaptive co-management indicators discovered are different from those noted in the adaptive co-management literature. Current literature within adaptive co-management, notes essential characteristics for adaptive co-management as; social capital (trust and leaderships) (Armitage et al., 2009; Folke et al., 2005), social networks and linkages (institutional support) (Armitage et al., 2009; Berkes, 2007; Folke et al., 2005), and a learn-by-doing approach (adaptive management portfolio) (Armitage et al., 2009; Armitage et al., 2007; Folke et al., 2005; Plummer et al., 2013).

Small-scale fishers in Purwoejo noted access to adaptable management portfolio in Table 11 as the number one most influential adaptive co-management indicator. This is similar to the current literature on adaptive co-management, which notes heavy importance on learn-by-doing approaches (adaptable management) within adaptive co-management (Armitage et al., 2009; Armitage et al., 2007; Folke et al., 2005; Plummer et al., 2013). However, small-scale fishers in Purwoejo noted community collectivity and delegation of authority as important influential adaptive co-management indicators intersecting their community. While current literature in adaptive co-management does not note these indicators as one of the topmost influential indicators for adaptive co-management. This is crucial as scholars such as Berkes, (2011) have been calling for increased SSF governance and management attention to determine the needs of these systems. This chapter helps provide increased awareness about the most influential adaptive co-management indicators within Purwoejo. While also stating the disparities between adaptive co-management indicator importance levels within literature, leadership and fishers in Purwoejo, aiding in the governance of this vulnerable SSF.

Fishery and institutional leaders within Purwoejo noted institutional support (social networks) and leadership (social capital) as two of the top three adaptive co-management indicators intersecting the community (see Table 11). These are similar to the most influential adaptive co-management indicators, social networks (Armitage et al., 2009; Berkes, 2007; Folke et al., 2005) and social capital (Armitage et al., 2009; Folke et al., 2005) as noted within the adaptive co-management literature. However, fishery and institutional leaders noted capital building as one of the most influential and important adaptive co-management indicators intersecting Purwoejo, over access to adaptable management portfolios (see Table 11). This is different from the current literature on adaptive co-management because current literature has learn-by-doing approaches (adaptable management) (Armitage et al., 2009; Armitage et al., 2007; Folke et al., 2005; Plummer et al., 2013), as one of the topmost influential adaptive co-management indicators in

social-ecological systems. Continued research within Indonesian SSF is necessary to further determine the adaptive co-management indicators that impact successful governance implementation as the needs of small-scale fishers and fishery and institutional leaders are different and evolve over time. This echoes the thoughts of Halima et al., (2019) who calls for increased governance attention in Indonesian SSF due to their unique structure.

Table 11 indicates that within the SSF of Purwoejo there are strong intersections with adaptive co-management indicators. Small-scale fishers noted in Table 11 that the 10 adaptive co-management indicators tested for within this chapter are present within their community. However, Table 5 indicates that the majority of small-scale fishers did not believe institutional support was present in their community as 197 fishers disagreed with it. This indication goes directly against what was discovered with fishery and institutional leaders in Table 6 as institutional support was identified as the most influential adaptive co-management indicator. This drastic difference in results for institutional support in the SSF of Purwoejo can be in part due to the low educational level of fishers and their inability to understand what support is coming from where and what is considered support. Interviews with fishery and institutional leaders mentioned in Table 7, note that there is institutional support from various institutions within the community. However, this is in form of training, education and knowledge sharing, while monetary support is in the form of subsidies (see Table 7). Interviews with fishery and institutional leaders in Purwoejo exemplify that there is institutional support within the community of Purwoejo. However, initiatives of institutional support need to ensure they are providing support to all fishers, increase educational levels, and include what support is being provided and from whom or what institution. This will help educate fishers on the institutional support that is being provided and intersecting the SSF of Purwoejo.

4.2 Adaptive Co-Management for Governance Transitions in SSF

4.2.1 Tambak Bulusan, Demak, Indonesia

Table 10 indicates that out of the 10 adaptive co-management indicators tested within this chapter small-scale fishers noted all 10 indicators intersecting their community. While fishery and institutional leaders noted in Table 10 that eight out of the ten adaptive co-management indicators are intersecting and present within the community. This exemplifies that current governance conditions of Tambak Bulusan can provide an avenue to transition to adaptive co-management. This applicability is fluid and if socio-political conditions deteriorate, and adaptive co-management indicators become less prominent within the fishery transitions of governance would be hindered. This is due to having almost all of the adaptive co-management indicators needed for successful adaptive co-management present and intersecting the community. By transitioning to adaptive co-management small-scale fishers can increase their adaptability to dynamic change within the fishery, improving their livelihoods and social status within Tambak Bulusan. This is essential as scholars such as Armitage, (2007) have noted that there needs to be increased social-ecological system adaptation in resources where livelihoods are linked to outcomes of the system. By transitioning current SSF governance in Tambak Bulusan to adaptive co-management the adaptability of social-ecological systems, such as SSF, can be increased. Transitioning to adaptive co-management within the SSF of Tambak Bulusan can additionally aid in managing dynamic changes that occur within the fishery. This is essential as Berkes (2011), and Halima et al., (2019), state that increased attention to how SSF governance can understand dynamic changes in social-ecological systems is crucial, marking the transition of current SSF governance to adaptive co-management as imperative.

Therefore, adaptive co-management is a viable governance strategy for the SSF of Tambak Bulusan due to the presence of adaptive co-management indicators intersecting the community. This brings further attention to SSF governance within Indonesia, which was noted by Warren & Steenbergen, (2021), and Halima et al., (2019), as a critical area for development within Indonesian SSF.

4.2.2 Purwoejo, Morodemak, Demak, Indonesia

Table 11 indicates that the SSF of Purwoejo has the majority of required adaptive co-management indicators intersecting their community. This exemplifies that the SSF of Purwoejo can have current SSF governance transitioned into adaptive co-management, as the indicators needed for successful adaptive co-management governance are present. However, strengthening the institutional support dynamics (see Table 7) within Purwoejo will increase the effectiveness of adaptive co-management governance. Increasing the knowledge of institutional support in Purwoejo will increase small-scale fisher understanding of where the support is coming from, what institution is providing support and how support is geared to aid fishers within the community. This would elevate small-scale fisher knowledge within Purwoejo, increasing the strength of the institutional support for adaptive co-management.

Transitioning current governance of Purwoejo to adaptive co-management can increase the fisheries adaptation to uncertain events. This has been marked critical, from scholars including, Armitage, (2007), that state, understanding ways social-ecological systems adapt to dynamic change is critical in areas that have livelihoods directly tied to the outcomes. Additionally, Berkes, (2011), explains increased attention is needed to understand how SSF governance can comprehend dynamic changes in social-ecological systems. Adaptive co-management can provide a viable governance approach for Purwoejo utilizing social learning (Armitage et al., 2009; Armitage et al., 2007; Folke et al., 2005; Plummer et al., 2013), social networks (Armitage et al., 2009; Berkes, 2007; Folke et al., 2005) and social capital (Armitage et al., 2009; Folke et al., 2005) to adapt to changing conditions within the fishery. This will improve the livelihoods of small-scale fishers who are directly tied to the success of the Purwoejo SSF. Adaptive co-management provides a viable governance approach for social-ecological systems, increasing adaptability of governance, filling in knowledge from the gaps identified by Armitage, (2007), and Berkes, (2011). Transitioning current SSF governance in Purwoejo to adaptive co-management will therefore provide an avenue to viability for SSF.

Therefore, adaptive co-management is a viable governance strategy for the SSF of Purwoejo, Morodemak, Demak, Indonesia. This generates new knowledge within SSF governance in Indonesia, which was noted by Warren & Steenbergen, (2021), and Halima et al., (2019), as a critical areas for research within Indonesian SSF.

5. Conclusions

In conclusion, this chapter identified the adaptive co-management indicators intersecting the SSF of Tambak Bulusan and Purwoejo, Morodemak, Demak, Indonesia. Increased attention was generated for governance of SSF within Indonesia, and the ability of current SSF governance within two Indonesian SSF to evolve from current forms into adaptive co-management were discussed. The objective of this chapter is to determine the adaptive co-management indicators present within two SSF in Indonesia to determine how adaptive co-management can be transitioned to as a form of SSF governance.

The 10 adaptive co-management indicators tested within this chapter provide insight into how to test for adaptive co-management intersecting SSF. Understanding how women in SSF view and feel adaptive co-management indicators can provide further avenues to viability as indicators will be tested across all genders, not only fishers. Adaptive co-management can provide viable pathways to transition SSF to viability because governance is understood through reflection, learning and social networks to determine the most effective and viable strategy forward. Transitioning SSF governance to adaptive co-management can provide an approach to spark the transition of small-scale fisher livelihoods from vulnerability to viability.

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Vulnerability to Viability (V2V) Global Partnership

The Vulnerability to Viability (V2V) project is a transdisciplinary global partnership and knowledge network. Our aim is to support the transition of small-scale fisheries (SSF) from vulnerability to viability in Africa and Asia. Vulnerability is understood as a function of exposure, sensitivity and the capacity to respond to diverse drivers of change. We use the term viability not just in its economic sense but also to include its social, political, and ecological dimensions.

The V2V partnership brings together approximately 150 people and 70 organizations across six countries in Asia (Bangladesh, India, Indonesia, Japan, Malaysia, Thailand), six countries in Africa (Ghana, Malawi, Nigeria, Senegal, South Africa, Tanzania), Canada and globally. This unique initiative is characterized by diverse cultural and disciplinary perspectives, extensive capacity building and graduate student training activities, and grounded case studies from two regions of the world to show how and when SSF communities can proactively respond to challenges and creatively engage in solutions that build their viability. Further information on the V2V Partnership is available here: www.v2vglobalpartnership.org.

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**VULNERABILITY TO VIABILITY
GLOBAL PARTNERSHIP**

